

CERTAINTY UHEL's DMP update 25.04.2025

Version 2

Description

The Data Management Plan (DMP) for cloud and precipitation remote sensing data created at the University of Helsinki is developed in the context of effectively managing and preserving valuable data generated for CERTAINTY project.

Funder

European Commission | | EC

Grant

CERTAINTY (101137680)

Researchers

Matti Leskinen (orcid:0000-0001-7842-4063), Dmitri Moisseev
(orcid:0000-0002-4575-0409)

Organizations

University of Helsinki, Finland

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [CERTAINTY UHEL's DMP update 25.04.2025](#)

Description:

The Data Management Plan (DMP) for cloud and precipitation remote sensing data created at the University of Helsinki is developed in the context of effectively managing and preserving valuable data generated for CERTAINTY project.

Researchers:

[Matti Leskinen \(orcid:0000-0001-7842-4063\)](#)

[Dmitri Moisseev \(orcid:0000-0002-4575-0409\)](#)

Organizations:

[University of Helsinki, Finland](#)

Contact: [Moisseev Dmitri \(dmitri.moisseev@helsinki.fi\)](mailto:dmitri.moisseev@helsinki.fi)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: [European Commission](#) | [EC](#)

Grants: [CERTAINTY \(101137680\)](#)

Project: [CERTAINTY](#)

3. License

License: [CC-BY-4.0](#)

Access Rights: [Public](#)

4. Templates

Descriptions

ACTRIS cloud remote sensing data

ACTRIS cloud remote sensing data used:

1. Cloud Radar observations
2. Lidar observations
3. Microwave Radiometer Observations
4. Disdrometer and weather station observations

The datasets collected at Hyytiälä SMEAR-II station (<https://cloudnet.fmi.fi/site/hyytiala>) will mainly be used for data analysis and method development. Datasets from other station will be used at the later stages of the project

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

Re-used

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Observational

1.1.5 What is its format?

netcdf

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

1 TByte

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To improve a product

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

The data is collected at the University of Helsinki Hyytiälä SMEAR-II station

,

Site information:

<https://cloudnet.fmi.fi/site/hyytiala>

Instruments:

<https://hdl.handle.net/21.12132/3.241bda142975460b>

<https://hdl.handle.net/21.12132/3.f360a2375f3e4e4f>

<https://hdl.handle.net/21.12132/3.191564170f8a4686>

<https://hdl.handle.net/21.12132/3.69dddc0004b64b32>

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

Researchers

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

Yes

[Vertical distribution of ice nucleating particles over the boreal forest of Hyttiälä, Finland](#)

Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics

ZENODO

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

Yes

<https://zenodo.org/records/15188640>

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

Yes

<https://github.com/actris-cloudnet/cloudnetpy>

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

- Data identifiers
- Researchers identifiers

DOI

ORCID

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

NetCDF Attribute Convention for Dataset Discovery

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

- Storage
- Re-use

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Dmitri Moisseev (orcid: [0000-0002-4575-0409](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4575-0409))

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

New cloud retrieval products

Using cloud remote sensing data we will derive new cloud microphysical and dynamical products that will be used to study onset of precipitation

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Observational

Two dimensional (height-time) data of cloud properties

1.1.5 What is its format?

netcdf

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

3000000000000

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To make informed decisions
- To combine with other data

Data will be used to study processes, interpret observations, and constrain aerosol-cloud interactions.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

University of Helsinki Hyytiälä SMEAR-II station:

<https://cloudnet.fmi.fi/site/hyytiala>

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- Education

Project partners

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

- a. Yes

[Vertical distribution of ice nucleating particles over the boreal forest of Hyytiälä, Finland](#)

Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics

ZENODO

b. No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

Yes

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10975295>

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

Yes

<https://github.com/actris-cloudnet/cloudnetpy>

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

NetCDF Attribute Convention for Dataset Discovery

The University of Helsinki research data will be stored using Fairdata IDA (ida.fairdata.fi) service.

It uses Research Dataset Description Tool Qvain (qvain.fairdata.fi) and etsin data finder (<https://www.fairdata.fi/en/etsin/>)

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

- Descriptive
- Reference

We offer descriptive metadata that enriches data or information resources with detailed information about their content, context, and structure, thereby improving their findability and practical use.

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

- Registry/Catalogue
- Metadata repository

The University of Helsinki metadata can be found in the national Finnish Fairdata services (<https://etsin.fairdata.fi>)

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

OAI-PMH

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

IDA Fairdata

<https://www.fairdata.fi/en/ida/>

Finnish National data repository

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

- Follows repository standards
- Details terms of use
- Has an open access content policy
- Supports retention

3.2.1.4 Add appropriate arrangements made with the repository(ies) where the described dataset will be deposited

This access is part of our institutional agreement with the repository, ensuring that the University of Helsinki researchers can deposit, access, and utilize datasets without any individual subscription or specific arrangements.

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.6 Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?

DOIs

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Cloud retrieval

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

Open

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Throughout the project's duration, the dataset might be subject to an embargo of up to two years. During this period, access to the data will be restricted, but project partners can obtain access using specific tokens. Once the embargo period concludes and the project is completed, the dataset will become publicly available, and accessible to all under the CC BY 4.0 license.

After the data become publicly accessible, it will not be possible to identify individuals who access the data. However, during the embargo period, access is controlled through tokens that are nominally issued to specific, selected partners.

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

Fairdata IDA (ida.fairdata.fi) is a continuous service for safe research data storage, offered free of charge to Finnish universities, universities of applied sciences and state research institutes.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

Yes. However, we will not have closed datasets

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

Direct links are provided

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

Yes

NetCDF Attribute Convention for Dataset Discovery

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

Yes

The dataset will be linked with the related scientific articles and also with the input data.

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

The embargo period is 2 years from the moment of publication.

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

- Readme files
- Codebooks
- Data cleaning
- Analyses
- Variable definitions
- Units of measurement
- Negative results sharing

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

Input data provenance will be linked in the metadata.

All the measurement equipment have PID

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

Data conform to format specification

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

- Storage

- Re-use

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Dmitri Moisseev (orcid: [0000-0002-4575-0409](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4575-0409))

5 Security

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

Passwords

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

- Data access
- Data storage
- Data transmission
- Data recovery
- Data sharing

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

Yes

7.1.2 Documentation of other procedures

All the minimum conditions listed in Science Europe Guidance Document are covered by the WP6 Open Science and Data management

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